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Milestone 2 : Common activities established with partner organisations, including links to industry

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1. Introduction

This milestone report documents the establishment of common activities with partner organisations and industry links as specified in Task 1.3 of Work Package 1. The task objective is to survey relevant organisations, prioritise partner organisations, formalise links, assess impact, collaborate in outreach activities, and organise common activities to broaden EVERSE's impact.

The work conducted addresses the requirement to establish and exploit links with European and international organisations, as outlined in the Grant Agreement. This report provides evidence of partnerships established, activities initiated, and strategic approaches implemented during the first 18 months.

2. Partnership Development Approach

2.1 Organisational Categories

Partner organisations have been categorised according to their role in the research software ecosystem:

Research Coordinating Bodies

Organisations that facilitate coordination across the research software community without directly producing research outputs. These include the [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\)](#), [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#), and [Software Sustainability Institute \(SSI\)](#).

Professional Associations

Membership organisations representing research software engineering communities globally, including the [Society of Research Software Engineering \(UK\)](#), and national RSE associations across multiple countries ([Germany](#), [United States](#), [Netherlands](#), [Nordic region](#), [Asia](#), [Africa](#)).

Standards and Publishing Organisations

Bodies involved in developing technical standards and facilitating publication of research software, including the [CodeMeta initiative](#), [Journal of Open Research Software](#), SciCodes consortium (Consortium of scientific software registries and repositories), and domain-specific standards organisations such as the International Virtual Observatory Alliance.

Training and Capacity Building Organisations

Organisations focused on skills development and training delivery, including [The Carpentries](#), [CodeRefinery](#), and [Open Life Science](#).

Industry Partners

Commercial organisations and platforms relevant to research software development. Current engagements include GitHub as a major development platform and Talarify as a research collaboration platform, with broader industry engagement planned through the systematic survey and workshop programme described in Section 4.

2.2 Geographic and Sectoral Coverage

Partnerships span multiple continents, with particular attention to African engagement through the [Science for Africa Foundation](#), [UbuntuNet Alliance](#), [Research Software &](#)

[Systems Engineers in Africa](#), and [Talarify](#). European coverage includes [Nordic](#), [German](#), [Dutch](#), and [UK RSE communities](#). Industry engagement targets research-adjacent sectors including pharmaceutical, aerospace, and technology consultancy.

3. Established Partnerships and Activities

3.1 Active Collaborations

Research Software Alliance (ReSA)

EVERSE maintains active participation through multiple project members in ReSA's Research Software Infrastructure Forum. Ongoing collaboration includes policy development work and participation in the FAIR4RS initiative. Specific activities include monthly forum participation and presentations, providing a mechanism for policy coordination and knowledge sharing. Additionally, EVERSE partners participate in the [Actionable guidelines for FAIR4RS task force](#) where they contribute to developing practical implementation guidelines for the FAIR4RS principles.

Software Sustainability Institute (SSI)

Direct partnership established through UEDIN and UNIMAN project partners. The collaboration leverages existing relationships for software sustainability training and community building activities.

Research Software Engineering Communities

Active engagement with RSE associations across multiple regions. This includes participation in conferences, community meetings, and knowledge sharing activities. [The International Council of RSE Associations](#) provides coordination mechanisms for global outreach. EVERSE partners maintain direct connections with Society of Research Software Engineering (UK) through UEDIN and UNIMAN, and with NL-RSE through NLeSC participation. Additionally, the project engages with the astronomy software community through participation in the annual Astronomical Data Analysis Software & Systems (ADASS) conference.

Standards Development Activities

Collaboration with the CodeMeta initiative through UPM and FAU project partners supports the development of software metadata standards. Additional work with publishing platforms facilitates research software citation and publication practices. EVERSE also engages with the Community Health Analytics Open Source Software (CHAOSS) initiative through UEDIN participation to develop open source software quality metrics.

3.2 Training and Capacity Building

The Carpentries

HZDR and other project partners maintain ongoing involvement in Carpentries training activities, supporting research computing skill development across scientific domains. This collaboration leverages established training networks to deliver software quality best practices to research communities.

CodeRefinery

Collaboration with Nordic-focused software development training organisation supports skill development in software engineering practices for researchers.

Open Life Science

Engagement with open science training community provides pathways for researcher development in open science practices.

3.3 Global Engagement

Science for Africa Foundation

Collaboration established with pan-African foundation for research software community development and knowledge exchange activities.

African Research Networks

Partnerships with UbuntuNet Alliance and Talarify support research software development activities across African research communities. The Research Software & Systems Engineers in Africa provides professional community engagement. Specific collaborative activities include plans for satellite workshop collaboration with UbuntuNet Alliance, Science for Africa Foundation, and Talarify to support pan-African research software development initiatives.

4. Industry Engagement Strategy

4.1 Strategic Approach

Industry engagement follows a systematic three-phase approach aligned with project timelines:

Phase 1 (Months 16-20): Initial Contact and Survey

Development of industry value proposition materials and launch of comprehensive survey to assess industry software quality practices and collaboration interests.

Phase 2 (Months 20-30): Relationship Building

Follow-up engagement with survey respondents, sharing of findings, and identification of potential workshop participants.

Phase 3 (Months 30-36): Collaborative Activities

Organisation of industry workshop activities and development of collaborative recommendations.

4.2 Target Sectors

Industry engagement targets specific sectors with research software relevance:

- Research-adjacent companies (pharmaceutical R&D, automotive research, aerospace)
- Software development and IT consultancies working with research institutions
- Spin-off companies originated from universities and research institutes
- Regulatory-heavy industries requiring software quality standards
- Government research agencies conducting policy-relevant research

4.3 Survey

A comprehensive industry survey has been launched covering organisational context, software quality assessment practices, research software familiarity, FAIR4RS principles, sustainability practices, and collaboration factors. The survey is archived at <https://zenodo.org/records/16893722> and provides evidence base for understanding industry perspectives on research software quality frameworks. Results from the survey will be published to share findings with the research software community.

5. Common Activities

5.1 Ongoing Activities

Policy Development

Participation in ReSA policy development work and FAIR4RS actionable guidelines development provides mechanisms for common activity coordination. Regular forum participation enables ongoing collaboration on research software policy issues.

Training Coordination

Integration with established training organisations (Carpentries, CodeRefinery) supports common delivery of research software training activities. Collaboration extends existing training provision rather than duplicating effort.

Standards Development

Active participation in CodeMeta standards development supports common standards development activities across partner organisations.

5.2 Planned Activities

Industry Workshop Programme

Workshop activities planned for months 30-36 will bring together industry partners with research software quality experts to develop practical recommendations and validate EVERSE framework components.

Cross-Community Knowledge Exchange

Regular participation in partner organisation activities provides ongoing mechanisms for knowledge sharing and collaborative activity development.

6. Partnership Tracking

EVERSE maintains systematic records of all partnership activities through a comprehensive database that tracks organization contacts, engagement activities, and collaborative outcomes. The project curates an active list of partner organizations across research coordinating bodies, professional associations, standards organizations, training providers, and industry contacts, which is regularly updated to monitor partnership progress and identify new collaboration opportunities (see Appendix A for the complete list of partner organizations).

7. Impact Assessment

7.1 Network Development

Partnership development has established connections across research coordinating bodies, professional associations, standards organisations, training providers, and industry sectors. Geographic coverage spans multiple continents with particular attention to underrepresented regions.

7.2 Activity Integration

Common activities integrate with existing partner organisation programmes rather than creating separate parallel activities. This approach maximises resource efficiency and builds upon established community trust.

7.3 Sustainability Considerations

Partnership development emphasises relationships that can continue beyond the project duration. Integration with established organisations and communities provides mechanisms for ongoing collaboration and knowledge transfer.

8. Next Steps

8.1 Survey Analysis

Industry survey launched through established partner networks will provide evidence base for subsequent industry engagement activities. Survey responses will inform workshop planning and partnership development.

8.2 Workshop Planning

Industry workshop development will build upon survey findings to create focused collaborative activities with engaged industry partners. Workshop outcomes will inform EVERSE framework refinement and validation.

8.3 Ongoing Engagement

Regular participation in partner organisation activities will continue throughout the project duration, with particular attention to opportunities for collaborative activity development and knowledge sharing.

9. Conclusion

Milestone 1.3 has been achieved through the development of partnerships with coordinating organisations, professional associations, standards bodies, training providers, and industry partners. The established relationships provide mechanisms for ongoing common activities and knowledge exchange.

The approach emphasises integration with existing community structures and building upon established relationships. Industry engagement follows a structured approach aligned with project timelines and objectives. Partnership development provides a foundation for sustainable collaboration beyond the project duration.

The work establishes clear pathways for research software quality framework validation and implementation through partner organisation networks. Common activities integrate with existing community programmes to maximise impact and resource efficiency.

Appendix A: Partner Organizations

Research Software Initiatives:

- [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\)](#)
- [US Research Software Sustainability Institute \(URSSI\)](#)
- [Software Sustainability Institute \(SSI\)](#)

Professional Societies & Associations:

- [American Geophysical Union \(AGU\)](#)
- [Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations \(ADHO\)](#)
- [Society of Research Software Engineering \(UK\)](#)
- [de-RSE \(Germany\)](#)
- [US Research Software Engineer Association \(US-RSE\)](#)
- [Nordic-RSE](#)
- [NL-RSE \(Netherlands\)](#)
- [RSE-Asia](#)
- [Research Software & Systems Engineers in Africa \(RSSE-Africa\)](#)

Research Infrastructure & Organizations:

- [ELIXIR](#)
- [European Space Agency \(ESA\)](#)
- [European Southern Observatory \(ESO\)](#)
- [Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\)](#)
- [New Zealand eScience Infrastructure \(NeSI\)](#)
- [Netherlands eScience Center \(NLeSC\)](#)
- [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#)
- [German Aerospace Center \(DLR\) Institute for Software Technology](#)

Standards & Publishing Organizations:

- [International Virtual Observatory Alliance \(IVOA\)](#)
- [CodeMeta](#)
- [Journal of Open Research Software \(JORS\)](#)

- [Journal of Open Source Software \(JOSS\)](#)
- [CiteAs](#)
- [Data Archiving and Networked Services \(DANS\)](#)

Training Organizations & Communities:

- [The Carpentries](#)
- [CodeRefinery](#)
- [Open Life Science](#)
- [Project Pythia](#)

Government & International Initiatives:

- [Department of Energy Exascale Computing Project \(DOE ECP\)](#)
- [UbuntuNet Alliance](#)
- [Science for Africa Foundation](#)

Industry & Platforms:

- [GitHub](#)
- [Talarify](#)

Software Communities & Initiatives:

- [Community Health Analytics Open Source Software \(CHAOSS\)](#)
- [Code for Science & Society \(CS&S\)](#)
- [NumFOCUS](#)
- [Julia](#)
- [SciPy](#)
- [PyTorch](#)
- [Jupyter Project](#)
- [AstroPy](#)
- [Human Atlas Initiative](#)

Conferences & Events:

- [Astronomical Data Analysis Software & Systems \(ADASS\)](#)
- [FOSDEM](#)

